

Popular Article

Critical Vitamins for Ruminants

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Abstract

Ruminants are those animals, who perform rumination or regurgitation of food. In every feed, nutrients are contained in the form of carbohydrates, proteins, fats, minerals and vitamins. Being a trace nutrient component, sometime livestock owner avoids to supplement the animal feed with these substances. Since ruminants possess rumen and ruminal microorganisms are capable of synthesizing water-soluble vitamins and vitamin-K. Therefore, only vitamin-A, D and E are considered to be as critical vitamins and must be furnished in the diet.

Introduction

Vitamins are defined as ‘a group of complex organic compounds, chemically unrelated to each other, present in minute amounts in natural feeds stuff and are essential to normal metabolism & lack of which in the diet causes deficiency symptoms. Vitamins can be grouped into 2 categories i.e., Fat soluble & Water-soluble vitamins. Both these vitamins could be differentiated from each other based on the following points.

Fat Soluble Vitamins	Water Soluble Vitamins
Vitamin- A, D, E, K	Vitamin-C & B complex Vitamins
Stored in body in fat depot and in liver.	Not stored in body except Vitamin B ₁₂
Excrete via faeces	Excrete via urine
Made of only C, H and O	Made of C, H and O, whereas some also contain N, S & Cobalt.

Since ruminants has rumen and ruminal microorganisms are capable of synthesizing water-soluble vitamins and vitamin-K. Therefore Vitamin-A, D and E are considered to be as critical vitamins and must be furnished in the diet. In general, most ruminant diets provide adequate amount of vitamin K and the B vitamins, either through natural feedstuffs or synthesis by microbial activity in the rumen. Thus, there are no recommended dietary concentration of these vitamins for ruminants.

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Some pertinent fact relative to critical vitamins in ruminants:

1. Vitamin - A

Synonym- Anti-infective vitamins aa

Vitamin A₁= Retinol / Retinal / Retinoic acid

Vitamin A₂= Dehydro-retinol

Functions

- Essential for formation of Rhodopsin i.e., Visual purple (photoreceptor for Vision especially in dim light)
- Involves information & protection of epithelial tissue and mucus membrane
- Essential for carbohydrate metabolism
- Essential for reproduction (in males for spermatogenesis & in females for normal reproductive cycle)
- In bone development for synthesis of mucopolysaccharides (as bone matrix)

Deficiency Symptoms

❖ Adult cattle

- A mild deficiency is associated with night blindness, roughened hair, scaly skin.
- Prolonged deficiency – excessive watering (copious lacrimation), softening and cloudiness of the cornea and development of xerophthalmia characterized by a drying of the conjunctiva.
- Constriction of the optic nerve canal in calves
- ROP & Infertility in breeding animals
- Abortion or production of dead, weak or blind calves
- Increased susceptibility to infection-calves (suppressed immunity)

❖ Ewes

- Night blindness
- Weak or dead lambs

Requirements – (Source: NRC)

Species & Class	Requirement (IU / kg body weight)	Requirements (IU / kg dry diet)
Lactating & dry cattle	110	4400
Growing heifers	80	2500
Young calves	-	9000
Goat	-	5000 (Morand-Fehr 1981)

Most Common Cause of Occurrence – Deficiency of vitamin A may occur when pastures are poor or when high cereal rations are used.

2. Vitamin- D

Synonym- Anti-rachitic factor

Vitamin D₂= Ergocalciferol

Vitamin D₃ = Cholecalciferol (Act as Hormone)

Functions-

- Necessary for absorption and metabolism of Ca & P.
- Also necessary for immune cell function
- Stimulates incorporation of P into phospholipid of intestinal mucosa

Deficiency Symptoms-

❖ **Young animals**

- **Rickets** with weak, easily broken bones, bowed legs

❖ **Young cattle**

- Swollen knees and hocks and arching of back

❖ **Older animals**

- **Osteomalacia** (uncommon) – resorption of bone occur

Requirements

- **Lactating cow:** 30 IU / kg body wt. (this would be supplied by diets with 1000 IU / kg DM)
- **Sheep:** 275 IU / kg in diet (NRC,1987)
- **Goat:** 1400 IU / kg dry diet (Morand-Fehr,1981)

Where, 1IU. of vit D = 0.025 µg of pure crystalline irradiated 7-dehydrocholesterol(D3)

Some Important Facts Related to Vitamin-D:

- Need is greater for pigs & poultry than cattle & sheep
- Vit D₂ and D₃ have same potency for cattle& sheep
- Animals housed indoors may need supplementation.
- More Vit D may be helpful managing milk fever.

3. Vitamin - E

Synonym- Anti-sterility vitamin

Tocopherol (4 forms-Alpha, Beta, Gamma& Delta)

Tocotrienols (4 forms-Alpha, Beta, Gamma & Delta)

Functions-

- Acts as natural antioxidant at the cellular level and play important role in biological redox reactions.
- Protects membranes against oxidative damage by free radicals.
- Interaction with Se containing enzyme glutathione peroxidase (GPx)

- Prevents muscle, liver and blood vessel degeneration.
- Role in development and function of immune system
- Aid in absorption & utilization of Vitamin- A

Deficiency Symptoms

❖ Farm animals:

- Muscular degeneration or myopathy also k/a muscular dystrophy associated with low vit E & Se intake in winter pd particularly noted in calves on spring pasture because of high PUFA

❖ Lambs& Kids:

- Stiff lamb disease

❖ Calves:

- White muscle disease
- Liver necrosis in calves due to loss of plasma proteins
- Reproductive failure in cow and ewes

Requirements: (Source- NRC)

Species & Class	Requirement (IU / kg body weight)	Requirements (IU / kg dry diet)
Lactating cattle	0.8	30
Dry cattle	1.8	90
Growing bulls	-	100 (NRC 1989)
Goat	-	100 (Morand-Fehr 1981)

Conclusion

Since most ruminant diets provide adequate amount of vitamin K and the B vitamins, either through natural feedstuffs or synthesis by microbial activity in the rumen. Thus, there are no recommended dietary concentration of these vitamins for ruminants. But remaining vitamins are needed to be supplemented in the ruminant's ration to avoid any serious implications.

References

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